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Mechanical Properties of Polystyrene Modified Asphalt Concrete Mixes from Single Face Compaction for Predicted Double face Compaction

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ABSTRACT

Mechanistic design of asphalt pavements necessitates initial material characterization of asphalt mix properties, employing various methods such as the Marshal Design and Hveem methods for mix design properties. This study utilized the Marshal Design method and indirect tensile test method to assess the mechanical properties of polystyrene modified hot mix asphalt concrete for both single face compaction and double face compaction under heavy traffic conditions. The research addresses key issues such as simulating actual field conditions with single face compaction, aimed at reducing wear on compaction machines and minimizing manual effort during laboratory testing. Preparation involved creating both unmodified and polystyrene modified asphalt concrete mixes for both compaction types. Findings indicate optimal performance with a 20% polystyrene addition across both compaction methods, with most properties meeting required standards. Laboratory-tested properties such as tensile strength, tensile strain, compressive strength and compressive strain were compared for the double face compaction from single face compaction results.

Keywords: *Polystyrene modification, asphalt concrete, single face compaction, double face compaction, mechanical properties, compressive strain, compressive strength, tensile strain, tensile strength, marshal stability*

INTRODUCTION

Mechanistic design of asphalt pavement always requires first material characterization. According to Brown and Foo [1] material characterization involves determination of elastic properties such as stiffness modulus that govern performance of asphalt concrete pavement with respect to distress behaviours. Previous studies have also revealed some of the various types of stiffness associated with mechanistic analysis of asphalt pavements; examples include resilient modulus [2], shear modulus [3], dynamic modulus [4-6] and elastic modulus [7].

It is also pertinent to note that proper material characterization is critical to accurately determine pavement performance. There are thus three levels of material property determination with respect to asphalt concrete mixes used in pavement analysis. The first level is the determination of the elementary properties of asphalt mixes which includes maximum specific gravity and bulk modulus of mix [8]. Secondly, characterization involves determination of mix design properties of asphalt mixes such as stability, flow, density, air voids, voids in mineral aggregates and voids filled with asphalt [9]. The third level of material property is the determination of mechanical and elastic properties such as stiffness modulus as mentioned above, tensile and compressive strains, tensile and compressive strengths of the asphalt mix.

Based on the discrepancy above the present study sought to investigate the correlation of both types of compactions by characterizing asphalt concrete mixes for polystyrene modified asphalt concrete in the laboratory by adopting SFC synonymous with field compaction and DFC akin to Marshal and Hveem design methods of compaction. During the construction of asphalt concrete pavement, laying and compaction of the asphalt

concrete is on one face usually above the ground level as a single face compaction on the pavement.

In effect the first concern is that laboratory compaction does not truly represent field compaction even though in theory compaction in the field is believed to draw from Newtonian third law of motion stating that there is an equal and opposite reaction when a force is exerted on a body. Secondly, laboratory compaction i.e., double face compaction akin to Marshal compaction exerts a lot of energy on the compaction machine and overuse of manpower such that wear and tear easily results. On this basis the present study sought to characterize asphalt concrete mix properties in the laboratory using single face compaction that will both reduce excessive use of compaction machine and manpower and at the same simulate true field compaction.

The aim of the research study was therefore to characterize the mechanical properties of polystyrene modified asphalt concrete mixes in the laboratory from single face compaction for heavy traffic category to simulate field compaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Compaction of asphalt concrete is an important process in construction of roads and highways and usually the last process in construction which when not properly carried out results in adverse effect on the pavement performance and durability. Therefore, monitoring compaction during construction is of grave importance to ensure adequate durability of pavement. Insufficient compaction leaves behind high percentage of air voids content which then initiates rutting to take place in a pavement [10], [11]. The current practice to evaluate effective compaction in the field is to check the density of asphalt concrete from cored sections of the pavement and compare with laboratory prepared

specimens to achieve certain degree of compaction as specified in the respective standard usually 90 – 95% of laboratory compaction. Density therefore is an important element in the construction of hot mix asphalt. According to Brown [12], there exists three primary methods of specifying density which are percent of control strip, percent of laboratory density and percent of theoretical maximum density [13]. Concerns that result from air voids intrusion due to improper compaction has led to other methods of compaction such as the use of super-pave [14]. Compaction helps to build a strong bond between layers and interfaces of hot mix asphalt (HMA) concrete mixtures; the use of higher compactive efforts like the super pave helps to reduce air voids while at the same time increase density. Researchers have attempted to show a relationship of bond strength between pavement layer interfaces [15-17].

Even though field-scale prepared specimens can replicate the site's actual conditions as precisely as feasible, they typically demand significant cash, which tiny research institutes cannot afford. Therefore, a laboratory-scale prepared specimen is frequently used, where the loose mix is compressed using a gyratory compactor or a Marshall compactor. Before applying the wearing loose mix in the compaction mold, the binder course loose mix for specimens manufactured using the normal Marshall process is compacted at double faces. The loose wearing course is then compacted. Sutradher has embraced this specimen preparation technique [18]. His research indicates that binder course preparation can be carried out in accordance with ASTM [19], subjected to double face compaction at 75 blows per face.

The quality of compaction of asphalt concrete mixes in the field during construction is usually to meet a 90 – 95%

performance of laboratory test result with respect to air voids and density. However, there is a procedural difference in compaction between actual field compaction usually carried out on a single face of the pavement being constructed and compaction in the laboratory usually carried out on both face of the asphalt concrete sample. Questions therefore arise on how to reconcile this procedural difference that clearly affects performance in both instances which is the core focus of the current study; on this basis comparison was made between properties of single face compacted asphalt concrete mixes and double face compacted asphalt concrete mixes [20], [21].

Compaction may also be impacted by the characteristics of the mix aggregate and binder. They accomplish this by influencing (1) how easily aggregate will reorganize under roller loads and (2) the binder's viscosity at any given temperature. The way aggregate interlocks and, thus, how easily aggregate may be rearranged under roller stresses is influenced by gradient. Aggregate size can generally be used to break down aggregate impacts on compaction [22].

The data in this article does, however, show a number of exceptions to these broad patterns. As evidenced by the difference in stiffness between the type of gyratory compactor (28-mm asphalt mixture) and the operation of roller compactors (20-mm asphalt mixture) [23], [24] also acknowledged that compactors within a given mode of compaction may manufacture specimens with quite different properties. Using a kneading compactor as an example, they claimed that several mixture attributes related to asphalt performance would almost surely be impacted by the compaction parameters (foot size, number of tamps, specimen size, layer thickness, and tamping pressure) and their fluctuation. The results

of Harvey et al. [25] further supported this viewpoint.

The basic objective of compacting asphalt concrete mixes is to obtain density in the mix sufficient to develop the necessary mechanical and elastic properties that will provide a durable and impermeable surface for the maximum possible life cycle of the pavement compatible with the inherent properties of the asphalt and aggregate components.

Scherocman and Acott [26] in their paper titled factors related to hot mix asphalt production, placement and compaction revealed the critical steps involved in the installation of asphalt concretes, the effect of compaction and the dangers of improper compaction. Their study showed that proper compaction creates a smooth, durable surface that can withstand traffic. In addition, that the goal of compaction is to increase the density of the asphalt concrete mix in order to provide a surface that is impermeable to moisture and long lasting. The study also showed that the degree and technique of compaction can have a big impact on the characteristics of the asphalt concrete mix, like air spaces, which in turn affects the concrete's performance in terms of fatigue cracking and rutting. Ultimately, their research was summed up by emphasizing three key characteristics that are directly impacted by appropriate compaction: less air gaps, enhanced bonding ability between the aggregates and the asphalt cement, and greater compressive strength. It is important to note that Linden et al. [27] and Mohamed [28] later confirmed the aforementioned findings.

Khan *et al.*, [29] studied asphalt concrete laboratory compaction methods to simulated field compaction. The main objective of their work was to compare different laboratory compaction methods to field compaction and to select the

laboratory method that was similar or close in compaction to that of the field. Five different methods of laboratory compaction method were analyzed including Marshall automatic impact compaction, Marshall manual impact, compaction, California kneading compaction, gyratory shear compaction with two different angles of gyration (1.25 and 6 degrees) respectively. The conclusions from their study revealed that the method of compacting asphalt concrete mixes significantly affects such engineering properties as air voids, bulk density and modulus of resilience.

The compaction of an asphalt mixture is greatly important for ensuring durable pavement performance. In the past laboratory compaction methods have been widely used to produce the test specimens which undergo testing to infer the behaviour of asphalt pavements in the field [30]. In order to ensure consistency of samples both on laboratory scale and from field, Liu *et al.*, [30] developed a new compacting device (Aachen compactor). In their research work the Aachen compaction machine and the Marshall compaction machine were comprehensively compared and evaluated using experimental tests, digital image processing and finite element methods. The conclusion from their study revealed that the newly developed Aachen compaction machine simulated field compaction above others with respect to mechanical properties of the concrete and therefore recommended that the Aachen compaction machine be adopted in the production of asphalt concrete mixes to be used in the field.

Luxman *et al.*, [31] carried out a research study on effect of compaction temperature on porous asphalt performance. The conclusions from their work revealed the following that the different compaction temperature has consequences for the

resulting density and mechanical properties. The reduction in compaction temperature increased the air void content and reduced the density. The decrease in compaction temperature has also decreased the resistance of the porous asphalt against abrasion loss, permanent deformation and moisture susceptibility.

Mechanistic design of asphalt concrete pavement will always require material characterization of the properties of the concrete. Also, construction of the pavement will require laboratory assessment by characterization of the desired properties that govern performance of the pavement in the field. In reality there exist a discrepancy between field compaction and laboratory compaction required for characterization of the asphalt concrete samples. Two major characterization methods used by almost all agencies and researchers in the determination of mix design properties have been by the Marshal Design method and the Hveem method [9],[32],[8]. However, both methods require compaction of asphalt concrete samples on both faces of the sample denoted as double face compaction which is contrary to actual field compaction carried out on one face of the asphalt pavement denoted as single face compaction. This discrepancy above between true field compaction and laboratory compaction have formed the basis of the limitation of previous other studies that have largely adopted the former in their research investigation.

Previous studies have mostly carried out characterization by adopting Marshal or Hveem Design method which requires compaction of asphalt mixes on both faces – double face compaction.

However, compaction on both faces of asphalt concrete mixes for characterization does not truly represent actual field compaction carried out on a single face of

asphalt pavements, hence the need for the current study. The bridge therefore, between previous study and current study is that the present study sought to characterize properties of modified asphalt concrete mixes synonymous with asphalt pavements by carrying out single face compaction in the laboratory which simulates true field compaction.

On the basis of the above the current study Characterized properties of polystyrene modified asphalt concrete mixes from single face compaction simulating true field compaction for heavy traffic category.

METHODOLOGY

Materials

The materials used for the research were Asphalt cement (binding material), Granite (coarse aggregates), Sand (fine aggregates) and Polystyrene (waste materials). All the materials were sourced from local dealers within Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Method

Mechanical properties

1. Tensile Strength

Tensile strength obtained from indirect tensile testing was used to characterize the stiffness of asphalt concrete mixtures and it is indicative of the strength of the asphalt concrete against fatigue, cracking and rutting. It is actually the strength of the material in tension. The Indirect tensile strength of the asphalt concrete samples was determined using Equation 1 below.

Where

$$\sigma_t = \left[\frac{2P}{\lambda d} \right] \quad (1)$$

σ_t = Tensile strength (MPa)

P = Load at failure (N)

d = Diameter of specimen (mm)

l = length of specimen (mm)

2. Compressive Strength

Compressive strength obtained from indirect tensile testing was also used to characterize the stiffness of asphalt concrete mixtures in terms of compression. The compressive strength of the asphalt concrete samples was determined using Equation 2 below.

$$\sigma_c = \frac{6P}{\lambda dl} \tag{2}$$

Where

σ_c = Compressive strength (MPa)

P = Load at failure (N)

d = Diameter of specimen (mm)

l = length of specimen (mm)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Strain of Polystyrene Modified Asphalt Concrete Mix

From Figure 4.1 below it was observed that the addition of recycled polystyrene to the asphalt concrete mixes for both single face compaction and double face compaction resulted in a linear decrease in

the tensile strain of the concrete mixes up to 20% addition of the polystyrene with minimal tensile strain values of 6.57×10^{-4} and 6.46×10^{-4} respectively at this threshold addition. Further addition of the recycled polystyrene waste resulted in an increase of both tensile strains. The inference from the research therefore is that threshold addition of polystyrene should be 20% for best performance. It was also observed that for all percentages of polystyrene addition double face compaction produced lower tensile strain values than single face compaction as expected due to level of compaction administered. The reduction in tensile strain can be explained by the phenomenon of void filling action of the polystyrene being a hydro-carbon and having high miscibility with the heated asphalt cement into the inter-granular spaces between the aggregates therefore reducing the inter-granular volume of voids spaces in the concrete mix. The closure within the void spaces results in stiffer and more compact mixes which in turn results in reduced tensile strains.

Fig. 1: Tensile Strain of Single Face Compaction (SFC) and Double Face Compaction (DFC) Against Polystyrene Content.

Compressive Strain of Polystyrene Modified Asphalt Concrete Mix

From Figure 4.2 below it was observed that the addition of recycled polystyrene to the asphalt concrete mixes for both single face compaction and double face compaction resulted in a linear decrease in the tensile strain of the concrete mixes up to 20% addition of the polystyrene with minimal tensile strain values of 12.85×10^{-4} and 12.15×10^{-4} respectively at this threshold addition. Further addition of the recycled polystyrene waste resulted in an increase of both compressive strains. The inference from the research therefore is that threshold addition of polystyrene

should be 20% for best performance. It was also observed that for all percentages of polystyrene addition double face compaction produced lower compressive strain values than single face compaction as expected due to level of compaction administered. The reduction in compressive strain can be explained by the phenomenon of void filling action of the polystyrene being a hydro-carbon and having high miscibility with the heated asphalt cement into the inter-granular spaces between the aggregates therefore reducing the inter-granular volume of voids spaces in the concrete mix.

Fig. 2: Compressive Strain of Single Face Compaction (SFC) and Double Face Compaction (DFC) Face Compaction Against Polystyrene Content.

Tensile Strength of Polystyrene Modified Asphalt Concrete Mix

From Figure 4.3 below it was observed that the addition of recycled polystyrene to the asphalt concrete mixes for both single face compaction and double face compaction resulted in a linear increase in the tensile strength of the concrete mixes up to 20% addition of the polystyrene with optimal tensile strength values of 2.58MPa and 2.97MPa respectively at this threshold addition. Further addition of the recycled polystyrene waste resulted in a decrease of both tensile strengths. The inference from the research therefore is that threshold addition of polystyrene should be 20% for best performance. It was also observed that

for all percentages of polystyrene addition double face compaction produced higher tensile strength values than SFC as expected due to level of compaction administered. The increase in tensile strength can be explained by the phenomenon of void filling action of the polystyrene being a hydro-carbon and having high miscibility with the heated asphalt cement into the inter-granular spaces between the aggregates therefore reducing the inter-granular volume of voids spaces in the concrete mix. The closure within the void spaces results in stiffer and more compact mixes which in turn results increased tensile strength.

Fig. 3: Tensile Strength of Single Face Compaction (SFC) and Double Face Compaction (DFC) against Polystyrene Content.

Compressive Strength of Polystyrene Modified Asphalt Concrete Mix

From Figure 4.4 below it was observed that the addition of recycled polystyrene to the asphalt concrete mixes for both single face compaction and double face compaction resulted in a linear increase in the compressive strength of the concrete mixes up to 20% addition of the polystyrene with optimal tensile strength values of 7.73MPa and 8.90MPa respectively at this threshold addition. Further addition of the recycled polystyrene waste resulted in a decrease of both compressive strengths. The inference from the research therefore is that threshold addition of polystyrene should be 20% for best performance. It was also

observed that for all percentages of polystyrene additional double face compaction produced higher compressive strength values than single face compaction as expected due to level of compaction administered. The increase in compressive strength can be explained by the phenomenon of void filling action of the polystyrene being a hydrocarbon and having high miscibility with the heated asphalt cement into the inter-granular spaces between the aggregates therefore reducing the inter-granular volume of voids spaces in the concrete mix. The closure within the void spaces results in stiffer and more compact mixes which in turn increased compressive strength.

Fig. 4: Compressive Strength of single face compaction and double face compaction against Polystyrene Content.

CONCLUSION

Based on the evaluation of the mechanical properties of the asphalt concrete mixes, it can be concluded that the incorporation of waste polystyrene significantly improved the structural performance of the material under both single face compaction (SFC) and double face compaction (DFC) conditions up to an optimum content of 20%. The mechanical properties assessed—tensile strength, compressive strength, tensile strain, and compressive strain—showed that increasing polystyrene content enhanced the resistance of the asphalt concrete to applied loads while reducing its susceptibility to deformation. Specifically, tensile and compressive strengths increased progressively with polystyrene addition up to 20%, whereas tensile and compressive strains decreased, indicating improved stiffness, better load-bearing capacity, and greater resistance to cracking and rutting. However, at 25% polystyrene content, a decline in strength and a corresponding increase in strain were observed, suggesting that excessive polystyrene adversely affected the internal structure and mechanical stability of the mix. Therefore, if only mechanical properties are considered, 20% waste polystyrene is recommended as the optimum modifier content for producing asphalt concrete with enhanced engineering performance.

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